

THE ORGANIZATION OF A ZOO IN THE CITY OF TERMIZ, SOUTHERN REGION OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: new changes in the 20s of the 20th century, in March 1921 in the life of the park of the Governor General of Turkestan, in September 17, 1933, the Regional Museum of Local History, Termiz Zoo, by the decision of September 30, 1947. Reopening of the garden.

Keywords: Termiz Zoo, Turkestan Governor General, G.V. Parfyonov, G.A. Zhuravlyov, Termiz district "Zhdanov" collective farm.

In the 20s of the 20th century, new changes began to take place in the life of our country, and a number of European enterprises and organizations began to be established. Among such organizations, one of the cultural and entertainment institutions, the zoo (airport gardens), began to appear.

In March 1921, a Botanical Garden was established in place of the Garden of the General Governor of Turkestan, and it was handed over to the Central Asian State University for conducting experiments and scientific research. University scientists organized an animal exhibition in the Botanic Garden, and based on it, the Tashkent Zoo was established. University zoologists such as N.A. Kayzer, N.N. Kuznesova, and V.B. Trizna contributed greatly to the establishment of the Tashkent Zoo. Tashkent Zoo was fully established as an independent institution in 1938.

Among such cultural institutions, a zoobotanical garden was established in the Surkhan oasis. On September 17, 1933, the regional museum of local history was established, and in May 1934, with the participation of museum employees and schoolchildren, a living corner with rare animal species was established in the museum courtyard. By June 7, 1934, the number of animals in the living corner of the museum reached 41.

Until July 2 of this year, admission to the museum was free. However, as of July 2, a paid entrance service was launched for visitors to the museum due to the need for daily feeding of the animals in the living corner of the museum. On July 20, 1935, by the decision of the district council, the Surkhandarya regional inter-district museum was transformed into a district museum. From the same year, the museum staff started the work of scientific study of old Termiz. It was also decided to allocate 10,000 rubles for the opening of a department of zoology at the regional museum and

for the expenses related to the maintenance of animals under the account of the department of zoology.

The director of the museum G.V. Parfyonov was on a business trip to Tashkent in order to strengthen the activity of the zoology department in the museum, he got to know the Tashkent zoo closely and studied their activities. After that, G.V. Parfyonov bought 2 bears, 3 wolves, 3 hyenas and other animals from the Tashkent zoo with the funds allocated for the zoology department and became the head of the zoology department of the Surkhondarya district museum. D. E. Aralov and the director of the Sherabad district museum of local history G. A. Zhuravlyov brought animals to Termiz. These first sent animals later served as the first exhibits of the Termiz City Zoo.

In 1936, the zoological department of the district museum successfully operated. In these years, the department of zoology was officially recognized as an integral part of the museum. The director of the museum G.V.Parfyonov, the head of the department of zoology G.N. Maksimov, the head of the department of scientific staff, G.A.Juravlyov, D.E.Aralov drew up a plan to turn the department of zoology into a zoobotanical garden, and in order to implement it, Orta The Director of the Botanical Garden of Asia, F.V. Rusanov, turned to the heads of the Moscow and Tashkent zoos, Professor P.A. Matafli and Associate Professor V. Kurbatov, and asked them for practical help. The idea of creating a zoobotanical garden in the city of Termiz was extremely interesting. Because the unique nature and animal world of Termiz, which cannot be found in other places, was considered the basis for creating such a park.

In 1936, the head of the zoological department of the museum, G.N. Maksimov, suggested a place near the meat processing plant on Narimanov Street in Termiz as a suitable place for the zoobotanical garden. That place was considered the territory of the collective farm "Zhdanov" of Termiz district. It is stated in the decision that the Termiz Zoo will continue its activities here from this year. By 1937, a decision was made to develop 20 hectares of land and 15 hectares of orchards allocated for the zoo in the activities of the district state museum.

Based on the decision of the Termiz City Council dated January 21, 1937, 20 hectares of land between the meat factory and the city prison was allocated for a zoo. G.N. Maksimov showed great zeal to create appropriate conditions for large animals in the allocated area. In order to create a garden and carry out landscaping works, 2 water pumping engines were brought from Tashkent city.

In 1938, another important event took place, that is, according to the order of the People's Commissariat of Uzbekistan, the zoological department of the museum was separated as a zoobotanical park with an independent legal status. Nevertheless, during 1938, it remained under the museum's control. By February 16, 1939, the zoological department of the museum was separated from the museum as an

independent organization and was named Surkhondarya district zoobotanical park. In order for the animals to live well and adapt to the climate, a reserve, fenced areas for keeping animals and poultry were built. Since 1934, the Maksimov brothers have not spared their knowledge and labor in the construction of the Termiz Zoo. They showed great commitment in the development of the department of various animals of the Termiz zoo, which took second place in the union.

On the eve of the Second World War, i.e. in 1942-1946, the Termiz Zoo was temporarily moved to the Tashkent Zoo, and on May 1, 1947, 35 animals were brought back and the Termiz Zoo was fully operational. From the first years of the Termiz Zoo to the years of independence, the people who contributed to the development of the zoo with their incomparable and grateful service did their great work to make this place into a wonderful and beautiful state.

The following managers worked at the Termiz Zoo:

1. V.N. Maksimov worked from 1934 to 1964.
 2. Tangirov temporarily in 1964
 3. V.T. Tyurin from 1964 to 1967.
 4. Garbunov temporarily in 1967.
 5. B.S. Khudoyberdiev from 1967 to 1970.
 6. N. Dehkanov from 1970 to 1971.
 7. S. Akobirov from 1971 to 1973.
 8. A. Musaev from 1973 to 1978.
 9. Kh. Makhmudov from 1978 to 2000.
 10. Ch. Sattorov from 2000 to 2006
 11. B.Kh. Toshboev from 2006 to 2014
 12. Ch. Sattorov from 2014 to 2017
 13. Q.M. Nabiev in 2017-2018
 14. K.N. Turopov in 2018-2019
 15. Sh.S. Ulashev in 2020-2022
- Ch. Q. Satorov 2022 today

These leaders worked tirelessly for the future of Termiz Zoo. In the first transition years of our independence, Termiz Zoo also experienced economic difficulties. But this situation did not last long. The leadership of our country and region paid more attention to this place and gave it a new look. 85 years have passed since the establishment of the Termiz Zoo of Hademay Surkhondarya region. As mentioned above, the glorious path of the Termiz Zoo has an instructive and rich history in all respects. We have set ourselves the goal of providing valuable information about this prestigious dargah, which has a history of almost 85 years, and about its path. On November 1, 1938, by the decision of the Council of People's Commissars of the UzSSR, the Termiz Zoo was opened and transferred to the

Department of Reserves, Zoos and Cities under the Soviet People's Commissars of the Uzbek SSR. In 1942, by the decision of the People's Commission of the UzSSR, the Termiz Zoo was closed. By the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR on September 30, 1947, the zoo was reopened. By the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR dated October 12, 1951 No. 2103, the Tashkent and Termiz zoos were transferred to the Committee of Cultural and Educational Institutions under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR. By decision No. 211 of the Ministry of Culture of the Uzbek SSR dated May 23, 1957, the Termiz Zoo was transferred from the system of the Ministry of Culture of the Uzbek SSR to the system of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR. According to the order of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR No. 911 dated June 4, 1963, the Termiz Zoo was transferred from the jurisdiction of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR to the Ministry of Culture of the Uzbek SSR. The zoo is a scientific and educational institution based on animal collections in all its activities.

In 1963, Termiz Zoo consisted of 5 departments.

1. Department of mammals
2. Department of birds
3. Department of fish and reptiles
4. Department of culture
5. Department of Botany (there is a farm and auxiliary farming).

The first processing of documents was carried out in 1962. The inventory included permanent storage documents from 1948-1958. All documents related to the Termiz zoo have been handed over to the state archive of Surkhandarya region. This inventory is a continuation of the inventory No. 1 of fund 459 of the state archive of Surkhandarya region. It includes documents from 1939-1980. Documents related to the establishment of the zoo were not accepted for processing. According to the decision No. 911 of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR dated June 4, 1963, the Termiz Zoo was transferred from the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR to the Ministry of Culture. Termiz Zoo is the largest in Central Asia in terms of individuals and species of animals, and it contains a large collection of domestic, allied and foreign fauna.

In 1979, Termiz Zoo consisted of five departments.

1. Department of mammals
2. Department of birds
3. Department of fish and reptiles
4. Department of cultural and public affairs
5. Botanical garden department

The zoo has a husbandry department and an auxiliary husbandry department, and the zoo is a research and educational institution based on its collection of animals in all its activities. The main tasks are:

a) carrying out scientific research work on common and wild animals and acclimatization of natural trees in the garden;

b) placement of animals in an environment as close as possible to natural conditions for habitats;

c) distribution of collections of biological science among the population, their application in the practice of national economy and formation of a scientific outlook;

g) Popularization of the Union of Soviet Creative Darwinism;

d) Daily upbringing and education work with children, study of zoology and biology through schools;

e) to conduct scientific and research work on the study of the most comprehensive specific forms and methods of exposure of live animals;

f) promotion of zoological knowledge and study of animal biology, improvement and maintenance of ecological condition;

g) to carry out scientific research and production work on the issues of animal nutrition, to conduct preventive laboratory activities aimed at preventing infectious diseases in animals;

The first processing of documents was carried out in 1962. Registration works include permanent storage documents from 1948-1958. The documents have been archived. These documents are a continuation of inventory No. 1 of fund 459, which excludes previously unprocessed documents and documents from 1939-1980. Since the establishment of the zoo, documents have not been accepted for processing. According to Lugovets, an employee of the zoo, the documents are kept in the personal archive of the first director of the zoo, G.N. Maksimov. The list is arranged in chronological order. All documents have been sent for processing. The peculiar aspect of the processing of the document fund is that the documents have been accepted for processing for a long time. This was done in 1962. Therefore, it is appropriate to include documents from 1939-1958 in this inventory. Due to the scarcity of such documents, documents /47 units are stored for several years. The proceedings do not comply with the existing regulations and do not follow the "Nomenclature of Cases". Guide materials, production and financial reports, business software master reports, staffing tables, form reports, etc. are left for permanent storage. In 1097 cases, the documents that are not of scientific and historical importance and have lost their practical value were selected for destruction, and a report was drawn up on them. Temporary storage documents (personnel materials) have been submitted to the zoo archives for safekeeping. "Sample list of documentary materials" was used in the processing of documentary funds. (M, 1969) So, in

conclusion, it should be noted that by the end of May 1934, a living corner with rare animal species was established in the courtyard of the museum. By June 7, 1934, 41 species of animals were kept in the living corner of the museum. Until July 2, 1934, the entrance to the museum was free for visitors, but due to the need to pay for the daily feed of the animals in the living corner of the museum, the issue of paying for the entrance of the visitors to the museum was raised. The zoology corner, which was established under the museum in 1934, began to operate as a separate independent organization by February 16, 1939. In a short time, thanks to the work of selfless naturalists, the zoobotanical park of the Surkhandarya region was able to find its place, and the country was enriched with wild and world fauna, and achieved great success. As of today, 85 years have passed since the establishment of the Termiz Zoo. As mentioned above, the glorious path of the Termiz Zoo has an instructive and rich history in all respects.

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